

Life
Seed
NEB

Co-creation plan

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1. Dynamics of the meeting

After the meeting to constitute the Seeders Groups, one or more working sessions were held in each municipality with this citizen group, with the aim of collaboratively planning the process of co-creation of the public space and the Bauhaus Kit.

The following aspects were discussed at these meetings:

1. Presentation of the results of the meeting to set up the group, with special attention to the SWOT matrix, which served as a context and starting point for the subsequent work.
2. Detailed presentation of the stages of the LIFE SeedNEB project, with emphasis on those related to co-creation.
3. Collective planning of the timetable of actions, with a special focus on the activities of the first months.
4. Collective development of the methodology for co-creation of the public space and the Bauhaus Kit.

The result of this last point was collected by the team responsible for the participation work package, and resulted in the methodology presented in the last section of this deliverable.

It should be noted that the Grant Agreement of the LIFE SeedNEB project states that the design of the SWOT matrix is a key element in the elaboration of the Co-creation Plan.

2. The meeting in the three municipalities

2.1. Lorquí (ES)

In Lorquí, the work with the seeders group was developed in two meetings, held on 12 December 2024 and 8 January 2025, with the participation of 13 people.

Based on the SWOT matrix and the communication analysis carried out in the meeting of 14 November, the stages of the project and its local impact were deepened. The involvement of the group, which has decided to take on a more active role than initially planned, is noteworthy, configuring this space as a stable platform for citizen participation in environmental issues.

The organisation of open days under the title "Lorquí Breathes Life" was proposed, with the aim of presenting both the Lorquí 2040 Greening Plan and the LIFE SeedNEB project. These days were held from 20 to 30 January 2025 with the collaboration of the City Council and local and regional associations.

During the preparatory meetings, the following issues were addressed:

1. Organisation of the "Lorquí Breathes Life" conference and distribution of tasks.
2. Co-design of the co-creation methodology.
3. Proposal of dates for the first stage of the Co-creation Plan.
4. Drafts of information leaflets about the workshops and the launching of the Bauhaus Citizen School.

The Lorquí Breathe Life conference took place between 20 and 30 January and counted with the collaboration of the seeders group, the City Council and various associations of the municipality and regional associations such as "Camino al Humanismo y a la Ciencia", "Lorquí Asociación Medioambiental", "ASPALO", "Avanza +", ANSE and AFEReM.

They culminated with the presentation of the Bauhaus Citizen School and the Greening Plan on Thursday 30 January and included tree planting, digitalisation of old photographs related to the municipality's natural spaces, a guided environmental route, workshops on the construction of wildlife shelters and a workshop on the study of Lorquí's bats.

2.2. Potenza (IT)

The second meeting of the Potenza Seeders Group took place on 12 February 2025 and was structured in two parts:

1. Visit to the Poggio Sinisgalli School, where the renaturation of the space will be carried out.
2. Co-creation workshop focused on the participatory design of sustainable maintenance solutions.

During the visit, accompanied by the teaching team, the intervention area was explored. The enthusiasm of the school for the project was highlighted, although concerns were also expressed regarding the long-term maintenance of the space.

The co-creation workshop addressed these concerns, seeking to turn the challenge of maintenance into an opportunity to strengthen the link between the community and the green space.

Strategies discussed included:

- Awareness-raising campaigns to enhance the value of the space as a common good.
- Active involvement of students, families and neighbours.
- Collaboration with the local business community.

- Alternative financing mechanisms (crowdfunding, sponsorship of green areas).
- Inclusion of the project in regular educational activities.

The third meeting, held online on 24 March, brought together 20 people, including planters, NEB facilitators and municipal staff. It was agreed to launch the Bauhaus Citizen School on 7 April and defined responsibilities, materials and the schedule of the event.

Initiatives such as the donation of plants and the use of planting materials as a symbol of environmental commitment were proposed. The idea is to present the project and the activities of the Bauhaus Citizen School through a press conference. Invitations will be sent to municipal and regional institutions, the staff of the Sinisgalli School, associations and local citizens.

The group discussed the idea of minimising the use of printed materials, considering the use of QR codes linked to the project website.

About the Co-creation Plan

The seeders and facilitators proposed to organise more than two events (face-to-face and online) in order to involve neighbourhood residents, association volunteers, parents and various stakeholders connected to the Seeders.

Dates were set for the simulation workshop and the outdoor co-design workshops (see point 3.2. of this deliverable).

The Bauhaus Citizen School activities will include a co-design process for the outdoor space with the participation of students and teachers, in collaboration with the school director, Prof. Gallo.

It was proposed to involve the neighbourhood through collective observation walks and site visits to the place where the redesign of the public space will take place.

2.3. Dunaújváros (HU)

In Dunaújváros, the group of seeders held its second meeting with the participation of 18 people. The aim of the meeting was to continue the work started in the first session and to advance in the participative design of the Cocreation Plan.

The topics addressed were:

1. Welcome and incorporation of new members to the group.
2. Review and validation of the SWOT matrix prepared in the first session.

3. Analysis of the previous communication diagnosis.
4. Collective work on the phases of the co-creation process and methodological adaptation to the local context.
5. Proposal for a calendar of actions and events linked to the Bauhaus School.

Despite not having planned a specific day as in the other two municipalities, the diversity of ideas and the commitment of the group was valued. Relevant methodological contributions were collected that contributed to the design of the common co-creation model.

3. Results: The Co-creation Plan

3.1. Methodology

Based on the proposals collected in the meetings of the groups of seeders from the three municipalities, the design thinking methodology has been adapted to the project.

The following objectives have been set:

- To generate collaborative ideas on how to improve urban spaces, and in particular the spaces to be intervened, through the integration of nature.
- To promote biodiversity and the accessibility of public spaces.
- Promote citizen participation, inviting residents to be an active part of the urban transformation process.

This approach is aligned with the principles of the New European Bauhaus (NEB), seeking to create more inclusive, sustainable and pleasant urban spaces, with an aesthetic that promotes the well-being of all citizens.

In order to adapt the timing of the workshop to a session that can be repeated with different audiences, the process has been summarised in four stages. It should be noted, however, that these serve as a guide for final adaptation to each of the contexts:

Empathise:

The workshop will begin with an immersion into the problems and needs of the local community, promoting an understanding of the context by reflecting on how public spaces can improve the quality of life of citizens. This involves understanding the impact of nature-based solutions (NBS) on their urban environment.

To this end, a battery of possible nature-based solutions for the improvement of public space (or that could be part of the bauhaus kit in the case of the kit workshops) will be presented, followed by photomontages that will act as simulations of how the space could look like with these interventions.

Fig 1. Example of photomontage.

From this point, the participants, previously divided into groups of a maximum of six people, will be asked to identify archetypical users of the places to be intervened, including current and potential users. To improve empathy with these people, they can even give them a name, an age and define their habitual use of the place.

Using cards like the one in the following image, they should identify the needs of these users related to sustainability, beauty and inclusion (NEB values).

REIMAGINING PUBLIC SPACES			
<p>INSTRUCTIONS FOR USE: Identify the potential users of the environment, both current and future. Write down their needs on a post-it note, always considering the three principles of the NEB</p>			
PRESENT OR FUTURE USERS	NEEDS (POST-IT)		
<p>NAME</p> <p>AGE</p> <p>WHAT USE WILL IT MAKE OF THE SPACE?</p>	SUSTAINABILITY	INCLUSION	BEAUTY
<p>NAME</p> <p>AGE</p> <p>WHAT USE WILL IT MAKE OF THE SPACE?</p>			
<p>NAME</p> <p>AGE</p> <p>WHAT USE WILL IT MAKE OF THE SPACE?</p>			
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Define:

Once the users and their needs have been identified, participants will be asked to define the main challenges that such a space faces in order to be truly inclusive for everyone and the opportunities that can arise through the integration of nature-based solutions.

REIMAGINING PUBLIC SPACES

INSTRUCTIONS FOR USE
 Write down the needs of the space on a post-it note, considering both current and future users.
 Classify them according to the themes proposed by the NEB: sustainability, inclusion and beauty.

SUSTAINABILITY CHALLENGE:

INCLUSIVITY CHALLENGE:

BEAUTY CHALLENGE:

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Ideate:

The next step will be to encourage creativity by brainstorming innovative and sustainable nature-based proposals to overcome these challenges.

REIMAGINING PUBLIC SPACES

INSTRUCTIONS FOR USE:

 Formulate a key question to achieve a more sustainable space.
 Write down all the ideas you can think of to solve it - all ideas count here, there are no wrong answers in the ideation phase!

SUSTAINABILITY ISSUE:
 How could we

BRAINSTORMING PROPOSALS:

Prototyping:

Finally, each group will have to design a project that they will implement by constructing a model of their proposal on a satellite image printed on an A1 poster using materials provided, such as coloured string, cardboard, plasticine, etc.

This will allow the groups to experiment and visualise their ideas in three dimensions, which helps to materialise concepts that would otherwise be abstract.

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REIMAGINING PUBLIC SPACES

INSTRUCTIONS FOR USE:
Start from the ideas generated in the ideation phase
Describe your proposal.

NAME OF THE
PROPOSAL:

DESCRIPTION:

BENEFITS:

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3.2. Timeline of the co-creation process

Lorquí

ETAPA	ACTIVIDAD	FECHA PROPUESTA
Co-Diseño (Ene 25 - Abril 25)	Taller de <u>simulaciones de futuro</u>	6 de <u>marzo</u>
	Taller de <u>codiseño</u> colectivo del <u>espacio público 1</u>	20 de <u>marzo</u>
	Taller de <u>codiseño</u> colectivo del <u>espacio público 2</u>	26 de <u>marzo</u>
	Taller de <u>codiseño</u> del Kit Bauhaus	3 de <u>abril</u>

Potenza

PHASES	STEPS	ACTIVITIES	DATE PROPOSAL	COMMUNICATION PROPOSAL
Co-design (Mar 25 - May 25)	Step 06: Launch the Bauhaus Citizen School at local level	1 presentation event	April, 7 2025 h. 16.30 POTENZA	Press Conference and Public Presentation Event for the Launch of the Bauhaus Citizen School Project Presentation of the Seeders/Facilitators Group and Best Practices Implemented at the Neighborhood Level. Distribution of Vegetable Seedlings by Students from a High School in Potenza. Poggio Tre Gallii Neighborhood Tour.
	Step 07: Co-Design the Nature-Based Solutions	1 Future analysis workshop 3 Co-design workshops	April, 14 2025 h. 16.30 April -May, 2025 28-29 april 15-16 may BAUHAUS CITIZEN SCHOOL IN POTENZA	Involving Seeders and NEB facilitators, along with the project staff from LUPT and the Municipality of Potenza. Three workshops in person, matched with two or more online, will be conducted with the participation of seeders, facilitators, and residents from the Poggio Tre Gallii District. Students from Sinisgalli's School will actively participate in a co-design project (during april and may), envisioning and sketching their ideal outdoor space
	Step 08: Disseminate Co-Design activities.	Info-day (Jan 25 - Jun 25) Green Beauty coffee (Nov 26 - Oct 27) Art Festival (Dec 26 - Jun 27)	JUN, 23 2025 h. 17.30 POTENZA	

Dunaujváros

PHASES	STEPS	ACTIVITIES	DATE PROPOSAL	COMMUNICATION PROPOSAL
Co-design (Jan 25 - Mar 25)	Step 06: Launch the Bauhaus Citizen School at local level	1 presentation event (Jan 25)	early of january	social media sites plus newspaper. leaflets
	Step 07: Co-Design the Nature-Based Solutions	1 Future analysis workshop 3 Co-design workshops (Jan 25 -Mar 25)	mid of january	monitoring
	Step 08: Disseminate Co-Design activities.	Info-day (Jan 25 - Jun 25) Green Beauty coffee (Nov 26 - Oct 27) Art Festival (Dec 26 - Jun 27)	ok or summer	social media sites, local newspaper, leaflets, forum of citizens in the pilot area
Co-implement design (Mar 25 - Jun 26)	Step 10: Co-implement the joint project.	1 Visit to the works in progress Co-implementation activities to promote fauna in buildings Beautifying at microscale	ok	social media sites, local newspaper, leaflets, forum of citizens in the pilot area
	Step 11: Verify the design of co-implemented actions in place.	1 working meeting	beginning of june	
Co-monitor & co-manage implemented NBS (Mar 26 - Nov 27)	Step 12: Co-Monitoring and verification of co-benefits.	9 Introductory workshops on urban bird observation, bats and pollinators monitoring 3 Introductory workshops on monitoring environmental and health values	ok	social media sites, local newspaper, leaflets, forum of citizens in the pilot area
Co-develop and replicate solutions (Mar 26 - Jan 28)	Step 13: Sustainability of the process	1 working meeting	„	

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4. Photographs Lorquí

Jornadas Del 20 al 30 de enero
LORQUÍ RESPIRA VIDA

Con el objetivo de promover la sensibilización y la acción ciudadana en torno a la biodiversidad, la sostenibilidad urbana y la mejora de las zonas verdes, el Ayuntamiento de Lorquí está trabajando en dos iniciativas para mejorar la vida de la ciudadanía:

Plan de Ecologización de Lorquí 2040
Se trata de un documento estratégico del municipio para el que se ha realizado un diagnóstico participado de la situación actual de las zonas verdes existentes y de las que potencialmente podrían crearse y se ha elaborado un plan de acción con 7 líneas estratégicas. **El 30 de enero se presentará a la ciudadanía el Plan de Ecologización de Lorquí.**

Escuela Ciudadana Bauhaus
Se trata de una nueva iniciativa creada en el marco del proyecto Life SeedNEB que coordina el Ayuntamiento de Lorquí. La Escuela Ciudadana de la Bauhaus será un espacio de aprendizaje en el que se ofrecerán diferentes talleres y actividades gratuitos relacionados con la 'Nueva Bauhaus Europea' y con el uso de soluciones basadas en la naturaleza para embellecer la ciudad y favorecer la biodiversidad urbana. **El 30 de enero se presentará la 'Escuela Ciudadana de la Bauhaus'.**

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Programación Del 20 al 30 de enero

- Lunes 20** Puesto informativo en el Mercado 10:00-11:30
Plantaciones de árboles con alumnos del IES "Romano García".
- Martes 21** Plantaciones de árboles con alumnos del CEP "Dolores Escámez".
- Jueves 23** Plantaciones de árboles con alumnos del CEP "Maestro Jesús García".
- Viernes 24** Café tertulia en el Centro de Mayores "Recuerdos del pasado"
Digitalización de fotografías antiguas relacionadas con el Saladar, la huerta, el río y la rambla.
Recuperación de relatos. Dinamizado por Leonor Gil Turstall-Tejada. 17:00-19:00
- Sábado 25** Plantaciones de árboles en la ribera con público general. 10:00-12:30
Lugar: ribera del río antes de llegar a la depuradora.
Scape room (de 12 a 18 años). Lugar: Pabellón Deportivo. Sala Escolar "Consuelo Monreal".
Inscripción necesaria a través del Qr.
- Domingo 26** Ruta guiada por el río conducida por ANSE 10:00-12:00
Salida Plaza del Ayuntamiento.
Puesto informativo en la Plaza de la Libertad. 12:00-13:00
- Lunes 27** Puesto informativo en el Mercado 10:00-11:30
- Martes 28** Taller de construcción de refugios para fauna. Dirigido a niños y adultos. 17:00-19:00. Lugar: Ayuntamiento. Inscripción necesaria a través del Qr.
- Miércoles 29** Taller LorQuióptera, únete al estudio de los murciélagos de Lorquí. 17:00-18:30. Lugar: Ayuntamiento.
- Jueves 30** **Evento presentación en el Auditorio Tierno Galván**

 - Presentación Plan Ecologización. 18:00-18:30
 - Presentación "Escuela Ciudadana Bauhaus" del proyecto Life SeedNEB. 18:30-18:45.
 - Presentación del concurso artístico "Lorquí Respira Vida". 18:45-19:00
 - Taller "cómo naturalizar" tu balcón/jardín. Regalo set. 19:00-19:30
 - Vino español 19:30-20:00

Plantaciones de árboles organizadas por la Asociación Camino al Humanismo y a la Ciencia con la colaboración de la CHS y Tragsa junto a los centros educativos. En la plantación del sábado también participan las asociaciones AFEREM, LAM, ASPALO, AVANZA+, ANSE.

Potenza

Planning

PHASES	STEPS	ACTIVITIES	DATE PROPOSAL	COMMUNICATION PROPOSAL
Co-Design (Feb 25 - April 25)	Step 06: Launch of the Bauhaus Citizenship School in the municipality	1 Launch event (Feb 25)	7 APRILE 2025 16.30	
	Step 07: Co-Designing Nature-Based Solutions	1 Future Analysis Workshop 3 Co-Design Workshops (Jan 25 - April 25)		
	Step 08: Dissemination of Co-Design activities.	Info-day (Jan 25 - Jun 25) Green Beauty Café (Nov 26 - Oct 27)		

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Dunaújváros

